

Architectural Enhancements and Feature Optimization of AutoVocoder for High-Quality Speech Synthesis

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Abstract—Neural vocoders are essential for producing high-quality speech in modern Text-to-Speech (TTS) systems. They directly affect how natural and clear the generated speech sounds. This paper focuses on improving the AutoVocoder by redesigning its architecture to better handle and process speech waveforms. The first step is improving data preprocessing to match the new architecture. This involves modifying how redundant audio features; notably phase and magnitude, are represented to provide cleaner inputs for processing. Next, the architecture is redesigned to include separate encoders and decoders for individual features. These specialized components are then combined into a unified encoder-decoder structure that learns the relationships between features, enabling deeper analysis and better synthesis. The goal is to achieve these improvements while reducing computational requirements. In the final step, post-processing techniques are used to enhance the quality of the generated speech. These methods are tested with noisy data to ensure the vocoder performs well under various conditions. This research provides a systematic approach to improving TTS systems, making them more efficient and reliable. The proposed changes aim to deliver clearer, more natural speech while maintaining adaptability for different environments and use cases.

Keywords—Speech Synthesis, Text-to-Speech, Acoustic Modeling, Neural Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Speech synthesis and acoustic modeling have been widely researched tasks, particularly with recent advancements in the implementation of neural networks. The ability to convert text into natural-sounding speech has deep implications in a lot of domains, notably virtual assistants, accessibility tools, and entertainment. Traditionally, mainstream Text-to-Speech (TTS) systems [1] [2] [3] use Mel-spectrograms as an intermediate representation for encoding speech waveforms. Mel-spectrograms provide a time-frequency representation that captures the main features of audio signals.

However, this conventional method is not without its limitations, prompting researchers to explore alternative approaches. A notable advancement in this area is the introduction of the AutoVocoder [3], which represents a shift in how speech is encoded. Unlike traditional systems that rely on mel-spectrograms, the AutoVocoder encodes speech using redundant audio features, thereby emphasizing the importance of accurate encoding in learning better representations of speech waveforms. This innovative approach demonstrates that the encoding techniques based on redundant audio features yield results that surpass the quality and efficiency of Mel-spectrograms.

The foundation of the AutoVocoder is built upon the principles of AutoEncoders, a deep learning approach designed to learn efficient representations of data through unsupervised learning. AutoEncoders consist of two main components: an encoder that compresses the input data into a lower-dimensional representation and a decoder that reconstructs the original data from this compact representation. However, despite its innovative structure, the AutoVocoder still faces several critical limitations that affect its performance and the quality of its outputs.

The first of these limitations is related to preprocessing. The current preprocessing stage is not effective enough in conditioning the input data for optimal encoding. As the quality of encoded output is heavily dependent on the input, improving the preprocessing pipeline could enhance both encoding efficiency and accuracy. Second, there are architectural constraints that hinder the AutoVocoder's ability to extract complex patterns in the data. While ResNet is employed as the backbone model, its architectural depth may not be sufficient for capturing the intricate nuances of speech. Moreover, the current handling of real and imaginary components during encoding lacks in representing phase and magnitude, suggesting that advanced methods could lead to better performance. Lastly, the absence of post-processing in the AutoVocoder presents a significant drawback. Post-processing plays a critical role in refining the output, allowing for noise reduction, error correction, and enhanced clarity. Without this phase, the AutoVocoder's outputs are more likely to retain noise and inaccuracies, lowering the overall quality of the synthesized speech.

The main contribution of this paper is exploring potential enhancements in waveform representation by addressing these limitations of the AutoVocoder. This includes improving preprocessing pipelines, reconsidering the architectural design to enable better pattern extraction, and introducing sophisticated post-processing techniques to elevate the quality of synthesized speech.

II. BACKGROUND

A. AutoEncoder

An AutoEncoder is a neural network for unsupervised learning and dimensionality reduction, aiming to encode input data into a lower-dimensional latent space and reconstruct the original input. It consists of an encoder, which maps input data to the latent representation, and a decoder, which reconstructs the input from this representation. By minimizing reconstruction error using techniques like backpropagation, AutoEncoders learn compressed, meaningful features without labeled data, making them ideal for tasks like feature extraction and unsupervised learning.

B. AutoVocoder

Most state of the art vocoders such as HiFi-GAN [1] and WaveNet [5] use the Mel-spectrogram; to encode audio data, however the AutoVocoder uses a novel approach, consisting of applying a differentiable variation of Short-Time Fourier Transform to break the audio into redundant spectral features: phase, magnitude, real and imaginary [3]. Providing these features allows this model to learn better representation of our audio data, instead of imposing and already established representation. For example, some features like phase could be more efficiently represented given the magnitude spectrogram [6].

1) *Pre-Processing*: Using a differentiable implementation of the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) in PyTorch, the audio waveform is converted into a spectrogram, which is divided into two components: real and imaginary spectrograms. These components are then used to construct the phase and magnitude spectrograms based on Equations (1) and (2), respectively.

$$magnitude = \sqrt{\sum_k Re(S)^2 + Im(S)^2 + 10^{-9}} \quad (1)$$

$$phase = \arg(\sum_k S) \quad (2)$$

The addition of 10^{-9} in the equation (1) for the magnitude calculation is to provide numerical stability and prevent potential division by zero errors. The value is chosen to be sufficiently small so that it does not impact the calculation.

2) *Encoder*: The encoder is based on a Residual Network [7], which is a deep learning architecture that has been widely used for image classification tasks. The key innovation of ResNet is the introduction of residual blocks, which allow the network to learn residual functions with reference to the layer inputs, instead of learning unreferenced functions [7]. The AutoVocoder implements a ResNet where each residual block consists of two 2D convolutional layers of width 3, followed by a 2D batch normalization and a ReLU nonlinearity. The network consists of 11 such blocks, the first five having 4 input and output channels, the middle one having 4 input channels but 1 output channel, with the remaining 5 blocks having 1 channel in and out.

Fig. 1. AutoVocoder's encoder resnet architecture

3) *Decoder*: follows a mirrored architecture, after decoding the latent representation into the original 4 channels, it reconstruct the waveform in one of the following three methods:

- *Cartesian*: The four channel-tensor is forwarded through a 2d convolution that outputs two channels, considered as real and imaginary, these two features are used to reconstruct the waveform:

$$y = iSTFT(real + j * imaginary) \quad (3)$$

- *Polar*: The same procedure as Cartesian, however the 2 outputted channels are considered as magnitude and phase, and used to reconstruct the waveform:

$$y = iSTFT(magnitude * e^{phase*j}) \quad (4)$$

- *Both*: The four channeled tensor is forwarded through a 2d convolution that outputs 4 channels that are used reconstruct the audio, by calculating polar and cartesian representations, and averaging them to obtain the input to the iSTFT.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Pre-Processing

1) *Logarithmic magnitude representation*: In the baseline AutoVocoder, the linear magnitude representation is used as one of the redundant audio features. However, for this paper, the logarithm of the magnitude was chosen. Using the logarithmic magnitude instead of the linear magnitude provides several advantages, particularly for neural networks, as it compresses the dynamic range of the audio signal, making it easier for the model to learn more details while maintaining the overall structure of the audio.

2) *Sine-Cosine phase representation*: an approach that was explored involved encoding the phase information using a sine-cosine representation (see Figure 2), which is particularly useful in this application since it ensures a continuous periodic encoding and helps capture periodic patterns, and it may improve the model's understanding of sequential/temporal data and its ability to capture phase-related features, as phase plays a significant role in determining the timing and tonal quality of speech [8].

Fig. 2. Audio waveform representation and pre-processing pipeline

B. Architecture

The architecture of the AutoVocoder was redesigned to address limitations in feature6 extraction and improve the overall efficiency of the encoding process. Key architectural components were modified to ensure that the model could better capture both magnitude and phase representations.

1) *Replacing ResNet with ConvNeXtV2*: The baseline AutoVocoder architecture utilized ResNet as the backbone for feature extraction. However, it was determined that ResNet did not provide the required depth and flexibility for capturing complex speech patterns. Therefore, ConvNeXtV2 [4], a modern architecture known for its superior performance in image and audio tasks, was adopted in Figure 3. The application of ConvNeXtV2 block is similar to what was used in BiVocoder [11], however instead of 1D convolution, 2d convolution is used, in addition to keeping Batch Normalization instead of adopting Layer normalization that is conventionally used in ConvNeXtV2 block architecture.

Fig. 3. Proposed ConvNeXtV2 block architecture.

a) *Depth-wise convolution*: applies a separate filter to each input channel independently [9]. This means each filter only interacts with one channel, not all of them, it will serve as a computation efficiency enhancement in the case of multi-channel tensor.

b) *Point-wise Convolution*: this activation function outputs a scaled version of the input based on its probability under a Gaussian distribution [10]. While ReLU is computationally efficient and simple to implement, Gaussian Error Linear Unit offers advantages in terms of: Smooth non-linearity, reducing the risk of dead neurons. Gradient flow, enhancing training stability.

c) *GeLU*: this activation function outputs a scaled version of the input based on its probability under a Gaussian distribution[13]. While ReLU is computationally efficient and simple to implement, Gaussian Error Linear Unit offers advantages in terms of: Smooth non-linearity, reducing the risk of dead neurons. Gradient flow, enhancing training stability.

d) *GRN*: The Global Response Normalization layer effectively normalizes the output of the preceding layer by computing a global response normalization, scaling and shifting it with learnable parameters, and maintaining a residual connection.

2) *Separate Phase and magnitude encoding*: A key advancement in the new architecture is the introduction of separate encoders for phase and magnitude. This design recognizes that phase and magnitude are fundamentally distinct representations of a speech signal, each containing unique information critical to understanding and reconstructing speech effectively.

a) *The Phase Encoder*: It is specifically designed to extract temporal and phase-related information from the audio input as illustrated in Figure 4. It focuses on the timing and progression of sound waves, capturing how they change over time. This encoder is adept at discerning subtle variations in timing that are crucial for phonetic distinctions and speech clarity. By isolating phase information, the Phase Encoder enhances the system's ability to track rapid changes in speech patterns, thus ensuring that the timing aspects, which are essential for natural speech perception, are preserved.

Fig. 4. Proposed Phase encoder architecture

b) *Magnitude Encoder*: It mainly focuses on the spectral features of the speech signal. It analyzes the amplitude of the sound waves across various frequencies, effectively encoding the energy distribution that contributes to the timbre and intensity of the audio. This encoder, as shown in Figure 5, specializes in identifying the harmonic content and frequency characteristics, which are necessary for distinguishing different phonemes. By focusing exclusively on magnitude, the Magnitude Encoder can optimize the extraction of features that characterize the loudness and frequency content of speech. The separation of these two encoders allows each to specialize in extracting their respective features more effectively. This specialization may lead to a potentially improved performance in encoding, as each encoder can utilize tailored algorithms and techniques suited to the specific characteristics of phase and magnitude. As a result, the system is capable of achieving more accurate reconstruction of speech, enhancing intelligibility and naturalness in synthesized speech outputs.

Fig. 5. Proposed magnitude encoder

3) *Unified phase and magnitude encoding*: Once the phase and magnitude have been independently encoded, their outputs are integrated through a Unified Encoder. This module, as described in Figure 6, combines the distinct outputs from both encoders, in addition to real and imaginary channels of the linear spectrogram. The output is then fed to a linear layer to obtain a cohesive representation of the speech signal.

Fig. 6. Proposed unified phase and magnitude encoder.

The Unified Encoder plays a crucial role in maintaining the integrity of the speech signal by ensuring that both temporal (phase-related) and spectral aspects are preserved and represented harmoniously. It effectively bridges the gap between the two domains, allowing the system to leverage the strengths of both encoders while compensating for any limitations inherent in treating phase and magnitude separately (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Proposed encoder architecture with all the sub-encoders.

4) *Proposed Decoder*: The decoder uses a mirrored architecture for effective signal reconstruction. The latent representation is expanded via a linear layer and processed through a unified decoder, which reconstructs combined features before splitting them into specialized phase and magnitude decoders. The phase decoder ensures accurate sine and cosine reconstruction, avoiding discontinuities, while the magnitude decoder preserves the spectral envelope and energy distribution. This specialized approach enables precise component reconstruction, resulting in higher-quality audio synthesis. The output phase and log magnitude are used to synthesize the waveform via polar iSTFT. The encoder-decoder architecture balances global and local feature processing, enabling component-specific optimization. CNBlocks enhance gradient flow and feature extraction over traditional ResBlocks, while dimensionality reduction and expansion maintain efficient processing without losing critical audio features..

Fig. 8. Proposed decoder architecture.

C. Post-Processing

For this enhancement, removing unwanted frequencies was essential due to a common limitation in the baseline AutoVocoder's synthesis process. While the AutoVocoder successfully generates high quality speech, it tends to produce output with higher amplitude than the original speech signals. This amplification inadvertently affects not just the desired speech components but also magnifies any background noise present in the signal. To address this issue, we implemented spectral gating through the noisereduce implementation [12]. Spectral gating operates on the principle of analyzing the frequency spectrum of the audio signal and applying an adaptive threshold to separate speech from noise components [13]. The process can be broken down into several key steps:

1) *Noise Profile Estimation*: The algorithm first estimates the noise profile from portions of the signal where speech is

absent, this creates a statistical model of the background noise's spectral characteristics.

2) *Threshold Determination*: Based on the noise profile, the algorithm calculates frequency-dependent thresholds, these thresholds determine which spectral components should be preserved or attenuated

3) *Spectral Gate Application*: The signal is transformed into the frequency domain using Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). Frequency components below the calculated threshold are attenuated, while components above the threshold, likely corresponding to speech, are preserved.

4) *Signal Reconstruction*: The processed spectrum is transformed back to the time domain using inverse STFT [2], the result is a cleaner signal with reduced background noise while maintaining speech intelligibility.

IV. EXPERIMENT

A. Training & Dataset:

We employ the same training criteria as the baseline AutoVocoder, with multi period and multi resolutions discriminators, in addition to a generator loss. For the training, we used the LJSpeech 1.1 Dataset [14], which consists of approximately 13,100 short audio clips of a single female speaker reading passages from 7 non-fiction books. The total audio length is over 24 hours, and each clip is accompanied by its corresponding text transcription, making it ideal for text-to-speech (TTS) model training and evaluation. The training was conducted on a university-provided server equipped with a NVIDIA Titan Xp GPU, using AdamW optimizer for 400,000 steps, that took approximately 100 hours to complete, during training, the speech clips were randomly cropped to 8000 samples, and a batch size of 16.

B. Evaluation metrics

1) *Objective metrics*: In this work, we employed five objective metrics to assess the quality of synthesized speech, these metrics include:

a) *Root Mean Square Error of Logarithmic Amplitude Spectra (LAS-RMSE)*: It evaluates the difference in the logarithmic amplitude spectra between the synthesized and reference speech. This metric focuses on how closely the synthesized speech matches the spectral characteristics of the original, impacting perceived naturalness.

$$\text{LASRMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{F} \sum_{f=1}^F (\log(A(f)) - \log(\hat{A}(f)))^2} \quad (5)$$

F: Number of the total frequency bins.

$A(f)$: The amplitude of the original signal at frequency f

$\hat{A}(f)$: The amplitude of the synthesized signal at frequency f

b) *Root Mean Square Error of F0 (F0-RMSE)*: It measures the accuracy of fundamental frequency (pitch) synthesis by calculating the error between the reference and synthesized F0 values. Lower F0-RMSE values indicate better alignment in pitch between the synthesized and reference speech, contributing to a more natural-sounding output.

$$F_0\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (F_0(t) - \hat{F}_0(t))^2} \quad (6)$$

T is the number of voiced Time frames

$F_0(t)$ and $\hat{F}_0(t)$ are the reference and synthesized fundamental frequencies respectively.

c) *Voiced/Unvoiced (V/UV) Error*: It measures the proportion of frames incorrectly classified as voiced or unvoiced in the synthesized speech compared to the reference 27 speech. This metric reflects errors in producing sounds that should either be voiced (like vowels) or unvoiced (like some consonants), impacting clarity. A lower V/UV error rate suggests better accuracy in capturing the voicing characteristics of the reference speech, contributing to better intelligibility and naturalness.

$$\text{Error} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T |V(t) - \hat{V}(t)| \quad (7)$$

$V(t)$ and $\hat{V}(t)$ are boolean indicators representing whether the original signal and the synthesized signal, respectively, are in a voiced or unvoiced state at time t.

2) *Subjective metric*: To evaluate the perceptual quality of the synthesized speech of our model, we performed MOSNet implementation that was trained on the VCC 2018 dataset obtained from the Blizzard Challenge [15]. MOSNet, with the large VCC dataset, has been widely utilized to enhance MOS (Mean Opinion Score) prediction for converted and synthesized speech. However, since our implementation utilizes LJ-Speech Dataset, which is why we are expecting low scores relatively to what is expected if MOSNet was fine-tuned or trained on LJ-Speech dataset [16].

V. RESULTS & ANALYSIS

As shown in Figure 9, both models synthesized high-quality and nearly identical Mel-spectrograms, with the proposed model demonstrating slightly better performance than the baseline in replicating F0.

Fig. 9. The comparison of Mel spectrograms and F0 values between the proposed, baseline AutoVocoder, and original speech. The transcript of the speech is “Handwriting experts from the FBI and Treasury Department testified that the writing on mall-order form was that of Lee Harvey Oswald.”.

The results of the objective evaluation for the baseline AutoVocoder and the proposed model are presented in the tables below. In Table I, bold and underlined values indicate the superior metric for each evaluation criterion. These findings highlight that the proposed AutoVocoder system incorporates more effective audio modeling techniques, achieving overall better performance compared to the baseline. While improvements in LAS-RMSE and V/UV Error are incremental, the significant reduction in F0-RMSE underscores the model’s superior pitch accuracy, which is critical for applications demanding high-quality audio synthesis.

TABLE I. OBJECTIVE EVALUATION RESULTS FOR THE BASELINE AND THE PROPOSED AUTOVOCODER

Model	LAS-RMSE (dB)	F0-RMSE	V/UV Error (%)
Baseline	7.34	0.170	3.48
Proposed	7.10	0.109	2.54

Table II displays the average MOS (Mean Opinion Score) evaluated by MOSNet for the baseline and proposed AutoVocoder. The bold and underlined value in the table represents the best score for the metric. The MOS results show that the proposed model achieves a slight improvement in subjective audio quality over the baseline, though neither model fully matches the quality of the original recordings. This modest gain in MOS aligns with the observed improvements in objective metrics, particularly in pitch and voicing accuracy.

TABLE II. MOSNET SUBJECTIVE EVALUATION RESULTS FOR THE ORIGINAL, BASELINE AND THE PROPOSED AUTOVOCODER

Model	Score
Baseline	3.01
Proposed	3.07
Original	3.11

To further assess the robustness of the proposed AutoVocoder in synthesizing audio under noisy conditions, Gaussian noise was added to the original audio before synthesis through both the baseline and proposed models. Table III summarizes the MOSNet subjective evaluation results for the original noisy recording, the baseline model, and the proposed model. Bold and underlined values indicate the best metric.

TABLE III. MOSNET SUBJECTIVE EVALUATION RESULTS OF NOISY SPEECH FOR THE ORIGINAL, BASELINE AND PROPOSED AUTOVOCODER

Model	Score
Baseline	2.93
Proposed	3.01
Original	2.99

The results demonstrate that the proposed model not only outperformed the baseline in handling noisy audio but also slightly exceeded the MOS of the original noisy recording. Specifically, the proposed model achieved a score of 3.01, compared to 2.99 for the original and 2.93 for the baseline. This suggests that the proposed model effectively enhances perceptual quality, even when synthesizing audio with

background noise, making it particularly suitable for real-world applications where noise is present.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presents novel advancements in enhancing the AutoVocoder for Text-to-Speech (TTS) systems by combining innovative data preprocessing, architectural improvements, and post-processing techniques. Key contributions include replacing ResNet with ConvNeXtV2, separating phase and magnitude encoders for deeper feature extraction, and implementing spectral gating for cleaner audio output. These modifications resulted in significant improvements in pitch accuracy, voiced/unvoiced classification, and perceptual audio quality, as demonstrated by MOSNet scores. The enhanced AutoVocoder exhibits robustness across varying noise levels, offering a versatile solution for real-world TTS applications.

Future work will focus on integrating F0 as a core feature to improve pitch control and reduce F0-RMSE error, enabling more expressive speech synthesis. Moreover, introducing attention mechanisms, such as self-attention layers, can address long-term dependencies, ensuring smoother phoneme transitions and greater contextual coherence.

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